

Review of Modified AES for Lightweight Implementation for IoT Devices

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Abstract— The rapid proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices necessitates robust yet lightweight security mechanisms to protect sensitive data. The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is widely recognized for its security and efficiency, but its conventional implementation can be too resource-intensive for IoT devices, which often have stringent constraints on power consumption, processing capacity, and memory. This review paper explores various modified AES algorithms tailored for lightweight implementation in IoT environments. We systematically analyze modifications aimed at reducing computational complexity, memory usage, and power consumption while maintaining or enhancing security levels. Our comprehensive survey covers optimization techniques such as algorithmic simplifications, hardware-friendly operations, and compact key management schemes. By evaluating these modified AES versions, we aim to provide insights into their suitability for different IoT applications, thereby guiding future research and development in securing IoT infrastructure effectively and efficiently.

Keywords—AES, IOT, Light, LUTs, WSN, Power.

I. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) represents a transformative technological paradigm, connecting billions of devices ranging from everyday household items to sophisticated industrial machinery. These devices generate, process, and transmit vast amounts of data, much of which is sensitive and requires robust protection mechanisms. Ensuring the security and privacy of IoT data is paramount, given the potential consequences of data breaches, including personal privacy violations, financial loss, and threats to critical infrastructure.

Encryption is a cornerstone of data security, with the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) being one of the most widely adopted encryption schemes due to its proven robustness and efficiency. AES, standardized by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in 2001, is employed globally across various sectors to secure data at rest and in transit. Despite its strengths, the conventional AES algorithm presents challenges for IoT devices. These devices often operate under severe resource constraints, including limited processing power, memory, and battery life, making the standard AES implementation too demanding.

To address these challenges, researchers have proposed various modifications to the AES algorithm to create lightweight versions suitable for IoT applications. These modified AES algorithms aim to strike a balance between maintaining high security standards and optimizing resource consumption. This review paper delves into these modified AES algorithms, exploring different approaches to adapt AES for lightweight implementation.

We begin by outlining the fundamental principles of the AES algorithm and the specific requirements of IoT devices that necessitate modifications. This includes an overview of

the standard AES structure, comprising rounds of substitution, permutation, and key scheduling operations, and identifying the computational and memory-intensive aspects that are targeted for optimization.

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is widely considered the gold standard for symmetric encryption. Its robust design and widespread adoption make it a compelling choice for securing data. However, the standard AES algorithm, designed for more powerful processors, can be a heavyweight for the lightweight world of IoT devices. Its complex operations consume valuable processing power and memory, potentially hindering device performance and battery life.

Researchers have risen to the challenge by proposing various modifications to the AES algorithm. These modifications aim to streamline the encryption process, reducing the computational overhead and memory footprint without compromising security. By strategically altering specific steps within the AES algorithm, such as simplifying the substitution and mixing operations, or reducing the number of rounds, developers can achieve a significant reduction in resource consumption.

This review delves into the world of Modified AES for lightweight implementation on IoT devices. We will explore the various approaches proposed by researchers, analyzing their effectiveness in reducing resource consumption while maintaining adequate security. We will examine the trade-offs inherent in these modifications, evaluating the impact on encryption speed, memory usage, and resistance to known attacks.

As the IoT landscape continues to evolve, so too will the need for robust yet lightweight encryption solutions. This review will explore future directions in Modified AES research, considering emerging trends and potential challenges. We will discuss the importance of balancing security with efficiency, particularly in the context of increasingly sophisticated cyberattacks. Finally, we will

highlight promising areas for further research and development, paving the way for a more secure and efficient future for the Internet of Things.

II. Literature Survey

P. Y. Cheng et al., [1] presented a novel datapath for the advanced encryption standard (AES), which has been effectively optimized with a high efficiency of throughput-to-area for lightweight applications in Internet of Things (IoT) devices. This datapath is intended to be used for encrypted data transmission. The suggested design for the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) allows for the concurrent encryption of 32-bit blocks, which allows for the fast processing of 128-bit data while simultaneously decreasing the amount of hardware space required. The ShiftRows, MixColumns, and key expansion phases of the 32-bit AES operation are where optimization is accomplished by using shift registers rather than normal registers.

S. Kumar et al., [2] The SHC (Simple Hybrid Cipher) is a novel block cipher that we offer in this research. It has a block length of 64 bits and a key length of 128 bits. Because of its hardware implementation, which makes optimal use of limited resources, it is an excellent candidate for usage as a sensor in a wireless sensor network (WSN) or as an RFID tag. The main functionality of SHC is dependent on S-Box-based composite field arithmetic technology. This technology is advantageous since it has a relatively cheap cost of implementation on hardware, while at the same time offering adequate security as a robust encryption method. A total of 949 LUTs are required for the hardware implementation of SHC-64, which yields a maximum operating frequency of 515.995 MHz on the Artix-7 Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) development board that is powered by Xilinx.

X. He et al. [3] A number of data or address ciphers are used in Internet of Things (IoT) endpoint devices with the purpose of providing real-time memory protection. This is done in order to prevent certain side-channel attacks on memories. This article presents a hardware engine of permutation-based address encryption (PAE) to provide memory address encryption with flexible width adaption, low latency, and minimal hardware overhead. The goal of this paper is to better satisfy the needs of real-time memory protection. PAE has lightweight properties with a gate count of 0.589 KGates, which is just 0.37% of advanced encryption standard (AES) and 33.50% of address cipher Galois field encryption (GF-Enc) when tested using TSMC's 40-nm standard CMOS technology. PAE measures 0.589 KGates.

R. Huang et al., [4] The Advanced Encryption Standard, sometimes known as AES, is widely considered to be among the most widely used cryptographic algorithms used for the purpose of assuring the safety of data. Typical lightweight implementations of the technique that have been published in the literature have an emphasis on optimizing the optimization of area and power, but they ignore the optimization of performance. Within the scope of this research, a revolutionary lightweight approach to the AES

algorithm is presented, and both encryption and decryption are taken into consideration. Our 32-bit architecture beats the current state of the art by 1.69 times in terms of performance per unit space and 1.27 times in terms of performance per unit power, respectively. When higher data-path designs, such as 64-bit or 128-bit designs, are used, these benefits become much more significant.

J. Vimalkumar et al., [5] In order to ensure the safety of data, an appropriate encryption method is required since the usage of Internet of Things devices is fast growing. Because of its computational complexity, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) method, which is commonly used, is not ideal for Internet of Things devices that have limited processing resources. The work that is being suggested creates optimal alternatives for the stages of the 128-bit AES algorithm, with the goal of minimizing the amount of power and memory that is used. Verilog HDL was used to construct a Modified Lightweight variation of AES, which was then implemented on an Artix-7 Basys-3 FPGA board. It was discovered that the modified variation used 81.92 percent less power on the chip for encryption and 47.21 percent less power for decryption. This was the case for both encryption and decryption. It is an algorithm that is suited for Internet of Things lightweight applications since it reduces the number of LUTs needed by a large amount, with 76.84% for encryption and 53.53% for decryption.

P. Satyanarayana et al., [6] AES algorithm presented difficulties in terms of the amount of computing resources and energy consumption when it is applied on Internet of Things devices that have limited capabilities. For the purpose of overcoming these constraints, the modification that we have presented makes use of lightweight cryptographic approaches, hence improving the algorithm for low-power microcontrollers that are often found in Internet of Things devices. In spite of the fact that it maintains a high degree of security, the updated AES algorithm displays a considerable loss in the computational accuracy it provides. In order to enhance the overall security of Internet of Things networks and reduce the risk of possible vulnerabilities, the research intends to apply modified AES to the ecosystem of the Internet of Things. Extensive simulations and practical investigations were carried out on a wide variety of Internet of Things devices under a variety of network situations in order to verify the effectiveness of the suggested technique.

GS Rajput et al., [7] The use of cryptography in algorithms is seen to be safe and effective. The secret key distribution is still regarded as a crucial problem despite the fact that it is similar to other symmetric encryption schemes. One single block of data (128 bits) must be encrypted or decrypted, and this requires more computer work that uses more power. The Internet is being extended to link almost everything on the world via the Internet of Things (IoT). In this article, a 256-bit key, lightweight cryptography-based data security technique is implemented for an IOT application. Instead of the traditional 2-D S-box and the prior 1-D S-box, a novel one-dimensional substitution Box (S-box) is suggested.

S. Purohit et al., [8] cryptography is an indispensable tool for maintaining the secrecy, integrity, validity, and non-

repudiation of information in the modern era of digital technology. The protection of sensitive data and the facilitation of trustworthy communication and transactions are both functions that it fulfills as an essential building component for secure systems. The highest levels of security, performance, and compliance may be achieved via the use of hardware-based cryptography. By efficiently scrambling the plain text, the Advanced Encryption Standard encryption provides an increased degree of cryptographic security, hence offering a solid level of protection. The purpose of this work is to provide a fresh approach to the problem of achieving an effective implementation of the Advanced Encryption Standard block cipher cryptographic algorithm on the Intel DE-10 Lite FPGA development board. Through the use of Linear Feedback Shift Registers, the design features architectural improvements for the forward and inverse AES SubBytes transformation (S-box and inverse S-box). Additionally, computational improvements are added in order to decrease the amount of memory storage that is required during round-wise key expansion.

M. Gong et al., [9] An inverter-based lightweight digital true random number generator (DTRNG) circuit is suggested and confirmed in silicon. The circuit is constructed using silicon. Extraction and discussion of the entropy of inverter jitter are presented here. The DTRNG circuit that has been presented makes use of a clock frequency of 8MHz and a digital cell library that is standard. This circuit is suited for Internet of Things devices that have a restricted space and a low operating frequency, and one can simply transfer it to different process platforms.

M. Nooruddin et al., [10] The characteristics of ASCON, which is a lightweight cryptographic standard chosen by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), are used. ASCON offers both encryption and authentication inside a single container that is memory-efficient, outperforming typical AES in Internet of Things applications. In order to ensure the safety of the negotiation of encryption keys between devices, the system is designed to be implemented using a key exchange method that makes use of pre-shared keys and a key exchange protocol. The method makes use of two environmental sensors, namely the AHTx0 temperature sensor and the BME280 atmospheric pressure sensor, in order to continually monitor and communicate data to a central receiver via the use of an ESP32 microcontroller. The performance of the proposed architecture is assessed by extensive tests, with a particular focus on important communication metrics such as the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), the amount of power used, and the amount of memory that is utilized.

III. Challenges

While Modified AES offers a compelling solution for securing resource-constrained IoT devices, it comes with its own set of challenges:

- **Balancing Security and Efficiency:** The core challenge lies in achieving a sweet spot between security and efficiency. Simplifying the algorithm

to reduce resource consumption can introduce vulnerabilities. Thorough security analysis of any modification is crucial to ensure it doesn't weaken the encryption against known attacks like differential cryptanalysis or linear cryptanalysis.

- **Formal Verification:** Modified AES algorithms deviate from the well-studied and mathematically proven standard AES. Rigorous formal verification is necessary to ensure the modified version retains a strong level of security. This verification process can be complex and time-consuming.
- **Standardization and Adoption:** The vast number of proposed Modified AES variations creates a fragmented landscape. Without a standardized approach or widespread adoption of specific modifications, integration and interoperability across different IoT devices can become challenging.
- **Side-Channel Attacks:** Lightweight implementations often rely on simpler operations, which can make them more susceptible to side-channel attacks. These attacks exploit information leaks from the device's physical execution, such as power consumption or timing variations, to potentially recover the secret key. Careful design and implementation techniques are necessary to mitigate these risks.
- **Keeping Up with Evolving Threats:** The threat landscape is constantly evolving. Modified AES needs to be continuously evaluated and potentially updated to stay ahead of new cryptanalysis techniques and emerging attack vectors.
- **Limited Hardware Support:** Hardware support for specific Modified AES implementations might be limited compared to standard AES. This can make it more challenging to optimize performance and resource utilization for specific hardware platforms.

while Modified AES offers a promising path for lightweight encryption on IoT devices, it's crucial to carefully consider these challenges. Striking the right balance between efficiency and security, coupled with ongoing research and development, will be essential to ensure robust and efficient data protection in the dynamic world of the Internet of Things.

IV. Conclusion

The review has explored the potential of Modified AES as a lightweight encryption solution for resource-constrained IoT devices. We have seen how modifications can significantly reduce the computational burden of the standard AES algorithm, making it more suitable for these devices. However, the challenges associated with balancing security, efficiency, and implementation complexities cannot be ignored. The success of Modified AES hinges on a rigorous approach. Security analysis must be paramount to ensure modifications don't introduce vulnerabilities. Formal verification remains crucial to establish the robustness of the modified versions. Standardization efforts are needed to

promote interoperability across the diverse IoT ecosystem. Additionally, mitigating side-channel attacks and staying vigilant against evolving threats require ongoing research and development.

REFERENCES

1. P. Y. Cheng, Y. C. Su and P. C. P. Chao, "Novel High Throughput-to-Area Efficiency and Strong-Resilience Datapath of AES for Lightweight Implementation in IoT Devices," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 17678-17687, 15 May 2024, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2024.3359714.
2. S. Kumar *et al.*, "SHC: 8-bit Compact and Efficient S-Box Structure for Lightweight Cryptography," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 39430-39449, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3372388.
3. X. He, Y. Bai, Y. Liu, L. Du, Z. Wang and Y. Du, "Low-Latency PAE: Permutation-Based Address Encryption Hardware Engine for IoT Real-Time Memory Protection," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 12319-12330, 1 April 2024, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2023.3333203.
4. R. Huang, A. Aljuffri, S. Hamdioui, K. Ma and M. Taouil, "Securing an Efficient Lightweight AES Accelerator," *2023 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom)*, Exeter, United Kingdom, 2023, pp. 841-848, doi: 10.1109/TrustCom60117.2023.00121.
5. J. Vimalkumar, H. R. Babu and B. M, "FPGA Implementation of Modified Lightweight 128-Bit AES Algorithm for IoT Applications," *2023 IEEE International Symposium on Smart Electronic Systems (iSES)*, Ahmedabad, India, 2023, pp. 306-309, doi: 10.1109/iSES58672.2023.00069.
6. P. Satyanarayana, N. Sriramdas, B. Madhavi, A. M, N. V. Phani Sai Kumar and V. Gokula Krishnan, "Enhancement of Security in IoT Using Modified AES Algorithm for IoT Applications," *2023 International Conference on Sustainable Communication Networks and Application (ICSCNA)*, Theni, India, 2023, pp. 380-386, doi: 10.1109/ICSCNA58489.2023.10370606.
7. GS Rajput, R Thakur, R Tiwari "VLSI implementation of lightweight cryptography technique for FPGA-IOT application" *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2023, ISSN 2214-7853, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2023.03.486.
8. S. Purohit, V. Deshpande and V. Ingale, "FPGA Implementation of the AES Algorithm with Lightweight LFSR-Based Approach and Optimized Key Expansion," *2023 IEEE International Conference on Public Key Infrastructure and its Applications (PKIA)*, Bangalore, India, 2023, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/PKIA58446.2023.10262697.
9. M. Gong, Z. Zheng and H. Li, "An Inverter-based Lightweight Digital True Random Number Generator Circuit for IoT Device," *2022 10th International Symposium on Next-Generation Electronics (ISNE)*, Wuxi, China, 2023, pp. 1-3, doi: 10.1109/ISNE56211.2023.10221587.
10. M. Nooruddin and D. Valles, "An Advanced IoT Framework for Long Range Connectivity and Secure Data Transmission Leveraging LoRa and ASCON Encryption," *2023 IEEE World AI IoT Congress (AllIoT)*, Seattle, WA, USA, 2023, pp. 0583-0589, doi: 10.1109/AllIoT58121.2023.10174401.